
Dignity & Respect at Work

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1. Introduction

Equity, diversity and inclusion are at the core of what it means to work and study at Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML).

We are committed to providing an inclusive environment ensuring all employees and students treat each other with dignity and respect.

PML's [Core Values](#) include “respect, responsibility and integrity” and the relevance of these to this policy is outlined below:

- **Respect:** Employees are expected to show consideration and thoughtfulness in relation to staff, clients, civil society and the environment.
- **Responsibility:** Employees are expected to act for the betterment of people, including our staff, and the environment on local to global scales;
- **Integrity:** Employees are expected to act with professional and appropriate behaviour; being honest in all that we do.

Bullying and harassment, whether intentional or not, undermines dignity and respect and PML takes such allegations seriously. Employees and students should have the confidence to report harassment or bullying without fear of victimisation.

No member of our community should experience any form of harassment including racism, sexism, ableism, homophobia, biphobia, transphobia, antisemitism, islamophobia or any other form of discrimination based on a protected characteristic or other personal circumstances.

Regardless of protected characteristic and other personal circumstances, all employees and students should be treated with dignity and respect.

2. Scope

This document applies to all PML Group employees, students, visitors and Trustees or Directors of the PML and PML Applications Boards.

Subsequent reference in the document to “employees” is intended to include students, and where applicable, visitors.

3. Definitions

Harassment	A form of discrimination. Harassment is often unwanted behaviour based on someone’s protected characteristic, sexual harassment or treating someone less favourably because they reject or submit to sexual harassment. Harassment can also happen without discriminatory motives. (See Appendix A)
Unwanted Behaviours	Behaviour which intends to, or has created the effect of, violating someone’s dignity by creating a hostile, intimidating, degrading, humiliating or offensive environment.
Bullying	Often identified as intimidating, malicious, offensive or insulting behaviour by one or more individuals. It may involve words, physical actions or general conduct. It can also include abuse or misuse of power. What one person may consider as bullying may be viewed as no more than firm management by another. However, any behaviour that leads to someone becoming stressed, demotivated or frightened is unacceptable. (See Appendix A)
Victimisation	Less favourable treatment of someone because they have made, or have helped someone else make, a complaint of bullying and/or harassment. (See Section 5)
Protected Characteristics	According to the Equality Act (2010), it is against the law to discriminate against someone because of their age, disability, gender reassignment, marriage/civil partnership, pregnancy/maternity, race, religion/belief (or lack of), sex and/or sexual orientation. (See Appendix A)

4. Process

If you are not being treated with dignity and respect at PML you have several options if you need to report an incident of bullying or harassment. This includes reporting incidents that may have occurred in online spaces such as social media or via email.

Throughout this process you are not alone you can talk to HR, your union representative or a wellbeing officer for support and advice.

4.1 Informal resolution

PML encourages all employees who believe they have, or continue to be, subjected to inappropriate behaviours, or if they have witnessed inappropriate behaviours, to raise their concerns at the earliest opportunity.

You should seek advice from the Human Resources (HR) Manager / Head of HR, your Trade Union representative or your manager in the first instance to discuss options in seeking a resolution.

It is recognised that this can be a stressful process and in addition to our internal resources, you can refer to PML’s Employee Assistance Programme, Care First, will be able to provide you with emotional support.

Informal resolutions may include you raising your concerns directly with the individual, options for a facilitated meeting or mediation.

Where an employee has witnessed inappropriate behaviour, they should raise their concerns directly with the individual concerned.

The aim at this stage will be for the inappropriate behaviour to cease.

It is helpful to keep a diary of details, dates, times, circumstances and witnesses to each incident so that examples can be shared in terms of what you have experienced as inappropriate behaviours.

4.2 Formal resolution

If the informal process has not been successful, or is not appropriate in relation to the circumstances, you should raise your concerns through the [Grievance Procedure](#) which can be found on the Intranet and documents within Pearl.

It is expected that employees will try and resolve grievances informally in the first instance. However, the Grievance Procedure should be used if you believe that you are unable to resolve the issue through the informal route and provides points of contact and timescales for a resolution.

You have the right to be accompanied by a fellow worker or trade union official at any meeting held within the grievance procedure.

For additional information and support, please contact the HR Manager or Head of HR, your manager or a Trade Union representative.

4.3 Hate crime/hate incidents

An incident of bullying and/or harassment may constitute a hate crime or hate incident. The term 'hate crime' can be used to describe a range of criminal behaviours where the alleged perpetrator is motivated by hostility or demonstrates hostility towards the alleged victim's disability, race, religion, sexual orientation or transgender status.

You may consider reporting a hate crime or hate incident via Devon and Cornwall Police.

5. Victimisation

Victimisation is when a person is mistreated because they have made, or intend to make, a complaint of discrimination (including harassment or bullying), or have helped another person to make a complaint under the Equality Act 2010 by providing evidence or information.

Victimisation can count as unlawful discrimination and result in disciplinary action, regardless of the outcome of the original complaint.

6. Support and guidance

If you are experiencing behaviours that undermine your dignity and are being treated with a lack of respect then you are strongly encouraged to report this but regardless of what action you choose to take, you will be supported.

The following services are available to you for further advice, guidance and support.

You can contact the HR Manager or Head of HR or your trade union representative confidentially for advice and support at any time.

PML's Employee Assistance Programme (EAP) is an employee assistance programme which is available to all employees.

This service offers support and guidance as well as 24/7 telephone counselling, cognitive behaviour therapy and much more. For more information, follow this link: [Care First](#).

7. Confidentiality

Human Resources and Prospect Union Representatives will treat information provided by the employee in confidence, unless withholding information puts any individual, property or premises at risk.

8. Procedure at a glance

Appendix A

These are examples of bullying, harassment, victimisation and more information on protected characteristics.

Bullying

Bullying can be described as threatening, abusive, intimidating, undermining or insulting behaviour that may be an abuse of power, position or knowledge. What one person may consider as bullying behaviour may be viewed as no more than firm management or strong personality by another and so may sometimes be difficult to define. However, inappropriate behaviour that leads to other people becoming stressed, demotivated or frightened is unacceptable. Bullying can take many forms, including social media, and all types are considered to be equally serious.

Examples include:

- Overbearing supervision, shouting, or verbal, written, online or other published abuse.
- Abuse of power or behaviour that causes fear or distress for others.
- Academic bullying, for example, asserting a position of intellectual superiority in an aggressive, abusive or offensive way, including by electronic media (for example, by email or on social media).
- Deliberately undermining someone by not allocating work fairly or constantly criticising them.
- Inconsistent management style where some people are favoured more than others.
- Public ridicule, sarcasm or humiliation.

Harassment

The Equality Act 2010 defines harassment as being *'unwanted conduct related to a relevant protected characteristic, which has the purpose or effect of violating an individual's dignity or creating an intimidating, hostile, degrading, humiliating or offensive environment for that individual'*.

The Equality Act 2010 bans the following three types of harassment:

1) Harassment related to the following 'protected characteristics' (as defined by the Equality Act 2010):

- Age;
- Disability;
- Race;
- Sex;
- Gender reassignment;
- Religion or belief;
- Sexual orientation.

2) Sexual harassment.

3) Treating an employee or student less favourably because they reject sexual harassment related to sex or gender reassignment or submits to it (tolerates it or allows it to happen).

Behaviour that is acceptable to one person may be unwanted by another. When assessing whether behaviour is harassment, it is important to look at if the behaviour, whether unintentional or deliberate, is unacceptable to the person on the receiving end and would be judged as harassment by any reasonable person. The word

‘unwanted’ means the same as ‘unwelcome’ or ‘uninvited’. The person the behaviour is directed toward does not have to expressly object to the behaviour before it is considered to be unwanted.

If the person responsible for the behaviour did not intend to create a negative environment, the behaviour will still be harassment if it has the effect of creating such an environment.

When deciding whether behaviour has had a negative effect, we will take account of each of the following:

- The view of the person who made the complaint. For example, whether they feel the behaviour has created an intimidating environment.
- Whether it is reasonable for the behaviour to have the stated effect. This is an objective test.

Employees and students can make a complaint of harassment if you find behaviour offensive and it relates to a protected characteristic. This applies even if the behaviour is not directed at you. You do not need to have the relevant characteristic yourself to make a complaint.

The Equality Act also protects people from harassment because of perception and association. This means it is still harassment even if the person does not have the characteristic but is wrongly considered to have the characteristic or is harassed because of their association with someone who has the characteristic, such as a family member, friend or partner.

Harassment may take many forms and includes behaviour related to a protected characteristic. However, harassment is not always related to any of the above. Examples of behaviour which is likely to be considered harassment are given below. This is not a full list, and we will view other forms of harassment equally seriously:

- Behaviour of a racist, xenophobic, sexist, homophobic, biphobic, transphobic, ageist, antisemitic or disablist nature.
- Any behaviour or abuse which may cause distress, such as name-calling, ridicule, insults, jokes, graffiti, physical abuse.
- Abuse through email, texts, websites or social media.
- Invading someone’s personal space.
- Displaying offensive material. This can be on paper or electronically (for example, on social media).
- Spreading malicious rumours or insulting someone (particularly because of that person’s age, race, sex, disability, sexuality, religion or belief, or because they are transgender).
- Preventing other people from progressing by deliberately blocking their educational progress or training and development opportunities or promotion.
- Intentionally isolating or excluding someone.
- Persistent, unwelcome contact, which may include text messages, emails, phone calls, gifts, letters, and calling at a person’s home or place of work or study.
- Stalking.
- Offensive sexual behaviour such as suggestive looks, leering and remarks (including on social media and electronic communication devices), offensive flirting, unwanted physical contact, unwanted sexual advances or demands for sex and compromising invitations.
- Offers of favourable treatment in return for sex (or threats of disadvantage if the person refuses).
- Making it public that someone is gay, lesbian, bisexual or transgender when they would prefer to keep this information private (known as ‘outing’).

- Making it public that someone has an underlying health condition without their consent (such as HIV)
- Drawing unwelcome attention to, or abusing someone's, religious beliefs including ethical veganism or a lack of religion/belief